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1. MS3.4 - Defining PID practices in FAIR data management

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3. Table of Contents

1. MS3.4 - Defining PID practices in FAIR data management	1
2. Versioning and contribution history	2
3. Table of Contents	3
4. Terminology	4
5. Introduction	5
6. Description of the Milestone	6
a. Role of the milestone	6
b. Means of verification	6
7. Integrated use case work on PID practices	6
a. PIDs in data production workflows	6
i. CNR	6
ii. INRIA	9
iii. UKRI-STFC	10
Challenges that need to be addressed	10
Expected impact of the Use Case	11
Expected outputs	11
iv. UNIMAN	11
b. PIDs in complex data citation	13
i. EMBL-EBI	13
ii. INRAE	14
iii. LifeWatch ERIC	14
c. PIDs and sensitive data	15
i. EMBL-EBI	15
ii. UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA ERIC	16
8. Conclusions and next steps	17
9. References	17

4. Terminology

Terminology/Acronym	Description
PID	Persistent Identifier
FAIR	FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
EU	European Union
KET	Key Enabling Technology
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
EGI	A federation of computing and storage resource providers
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
SWHID	SoftWare Hash IDentifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
CWL	Common Workflow Language
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
API	Application Programming Interface
WCI	Workflows Community Initiative
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ORCID iD	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry

5. Introduction

The top priority for this task is identifying user needs and PID practices in different scientific communities. Thus, this task focuses on the FAIR-IMPACT integrated use cases and use cases from other stakeholders to support research communities in establishing best practices around PID minting practices for different types of datasets, workflows and research objects, leading to more exact data citation and a broader and more targeted use of PIDs. The PID practices will be explored from the viewpoint of PIDs in data production workflows, PIDs in complex data citation and PIDs for sensitive data. The work on PIDs in data production workflows will focus on e.g. data products, automatic workflows, documenting data provenance in processes and PIDs for instruments, software etc. PIDs in complex data citation involve looking into ways in which different types of entities, including versioning, collections and hierarchies, affect PID minting practices in data citation. Lastly, the work on PID practices when dealing with sensitive data focuses on specific needs regarding kernel metadata and related owner rights. By engaging with the three user-centric integrated use cases, these cross-cutting themes will be considered:

1. Scientific reproducibility and machine actionability,
2. Research object type definitions for persistent identification, such as instruments, devices, software and services, and
3. Granularity, identifier syntax and relations

Opportunities for community engagement are realised through three workshops dedicated to these themes. The workshop outcome will further enrich the use case documentation and provide user-friendly documentation and validation to the results. All end-user documentation will be shared across communities, resulting in harmonised PID practices.

6. Description of the Milestone

a. Role of the milestone

This milestone, *MS3.4 Defining PID practices in FAIR data management*, delivers a first set of descriptions on good practices for implementing PIDs in FAIR data management. This milestone is setting the scene for the forthcoming progress updates (D3.2 User guidelines on EOSC PID implementation) and can be considered as an introduction to the use case partners' work on advancing PIDs. Furthermore, this milestone report feeds into the work of T3.1.

b. Means of verification

All eight integrated use case partners have provided a short introduction on their organisation, a status report on the work already completed, and the plans for the immediate future.

7. Integrated use case work on PID practices

a. PIDs in data production workflows

i. CNR

In the “European Strategy for Key Enabling Technologies”, the EU has defined six Key Enabling Technologies (KETs): micro and nanoelectronics, nanotechnology, industrial biotechnology, advanced materials, photonics, and advanced manufacturing technologies.

The ability to master micro- and nano-fabrication processes is of strategic importance, not only to be able to produce major research breakthroughs, but also to achieve leadership in developing the leading applications and thus gaining initial market share for next generation micro/nano devices in markets such as smart systems, internet of things, health, energy, food, automotive, and consumer electronics.

CNR is the largest public research institution in Italy and holds the largest ensemble of cutting-edge micro and nanofabrication facilities for the manufacture of microelectronic devices and microsystems for both industrial and research purposes.

In the vision of establishing European-level infrastructures and research competencies in micro-nano-manufacturing to enhance quality, efficiency, rapid knowledge sharing, and the relevance of European basic research in nanotechnologies, it is vital to build a FAIR management of technological processes.

In general, the path to creating a generic device or microsystem from a slice of material (such as Silicon, Germanium, SiC, etc.) consists of a series of cycles (generically called technological steps that can be repeated dozens or hundreds of times):

- Addition of materials (deposition)
- Removal, including selective removal, of materials (etching)
- Transferring a geometry onto the slice (pattern lithography)

Each of these steps can also consist of a high number of elementary steps. For each elementary step, different sets of parameters can be associated.

The laboratories where these activities are carried out (called Clean Rooms) themselves have an impact on the type of data to be managed. For instance, for each laboratory or part of it, some fundamental parameters can be defined:

- Cleanliness level of the environment (defined as ISO class)
- Specific access rules to laboratories for external personnel
- Constraints on the use of materials (copper, organic material, etc.)

The same basic principles for constructing FAIR data also apply in the field of micro-nano-manufacturing: there must be superstructures that are PIDs (for data, metadata,

etc.), a detailed description of the object to be shared is necessary (data and technologies, for example), and implementing accessible and reusable metadata descriptor standards is required. This also implies introducing constraints in the choice of repositories, data, or software that are as standard and searchable as possible on the network.

It is important to highlight that not all data produced can be or is shared (we refer to modulation of sharing) and they identify a static part of the infrastructure: what to represent, what to share, which indicators to use, vocabularies, and descriptors to then build what will be the ontology of the activity and thus the description of how the objects interact with each other. For example, a machine performs an action: it is crucial that this action is represented in a way that is understandable through a web query and interpretable without ambiguity by every user.

The use case's goal is to create a specific standard in the field of micro- and nano-manufacturing, as has been done in characterization (CHADA) and modelling (MODA) in the development of materials and nanomaterials, without necessarily creating a completely new data management system but drawing from activities already quite mature in the field of nanosciences.

This approach has two main purposes: significantly reducing implementation times and, more importantly, creating interoperable standards and implementing a FAIR schema capable of managing and producing data that can be input or benefit from existing data processing in MODA and CHADA. For instance, communities studying new materials can provide useful information for the development of a particular manufacturing technological process or produce and provide data of interest in the characterization or simulation of new materials.

As anticipated in the introduction, the process to create a device or microsystem is composed of a complex sequence of cycles, consisting of a high number of process steps. The idea is to break down a generic step in the micro-nano manufacturing into sub-steps that can already be represented and modelled based on the CHADA paradigm.

The first fundamental step towards creating a "common vocabulary" is to converge on definitions, constraints, rules, or common recipes for a large part of the community involved in micro- and nano-manufacturing.

The reality of laboratories involved in micro and nano-manufacturing is extensive and distributed throughout Europe. Interaction between laboratories will provide invaluable support for validating the structure being developed, aiding in constructing a FAIR data system that will have a very broad, established, and significant community.

ii. INRIA

Software identification refers to multiple practices depending if the focus is more on describing (i.e. attributing credit to authors) or on referencing software. PIDs used to reference data sets, such as DOIs, are useful to reference a software as a project (i.e. the software as a concept, not a digital object). But referencing software artefacts (i.e. digital objects) with different levels of granularity calls for specific identifiers. Therefore, identifiers in Software Heritage allow to reference a specific version of the source code of a project, at different levels of granularity: a snapshot, a release, a directory, down to a single file.

[Software Heritage](#) is an international non-for-profit shared infrastructure supported by UNESCO and INRIA. Software Heritage's core missions are to collect, preserve and share the source code that is publicly available. The development history is permanently archived along the source code, in a uniform data model.

Software Heritage ensures availability and traceability of software by attributing persistent and intrinsic identifiers called SWHIDs ("SoftWare Hash IDentifiers") to software source code artefacts. Currently, over 30 billion software artefacts in the Software Heritage archive are identified using SWHIDs.

SWHID addresses the challenge of dealing with the different level of granularity of software artefacts: source code files, source trees, commits, and other objects typically found in version control systems. SWHID is a PID, independent of the development platform or technology, that can be computed from the designated object itself without needing a register to maintain the correspondence.

The proposal is to advance the use of SWHID for referencing software source code artifacts.

SWHID are [unique identifiers](#) intrinsically bound to the software components. The difference between extrinsic and intrinsic identifiers lies in the way the relation between identifier and designated object is created and maintained. SWHID don't rely on an external register. Thus, end-users can recompute identifiers on retrieved objects and verify the match.

The attribution of SWHID raises the fact that deduplication has to be built-in, the database of the archive itself has to implement an ad hoc data model. Thus, any software artefacts encountered in the wild gets added to Software Heritage only if a corresponding node with a matching intrinsic identifier is not already available in the graph—file content, commits, entire directories or project snapshots are all deduplicated, incurring storage costs only once.

An agreement on a standard therefore, in June 2023, a [first stable version of the SWHID specification was published](#): it describes precisely how SWHIDs are computed. A [working](#)

[group](#) gathering experts from different institutions had been [launched in March 2023](#). The relevance of SWHIDs goes way beyond source code and Software Heritage.

The FAIR-IMPACT project is an opportunity to elaborate compelling use cases in order to help the stakeholders adopt best practices for software referencing. This use case is domain agnostic: software referencing is a shared challenge for researchers in all academic fields using computing. Non-developers end-users are also included in the scope because they need to refer to the source code authored by others, such as they do when they use other academic outputs such as data sets, bibliographic records, etc. Alongside the work on the SWHID specification, an important stake is to help end-users navigating through PIDs for software.

iii. UKRI-STFC

The FAIR-IMPACT members from the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), part of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), work with photon and neutron (PaN) large-scale scientific facilities (research infrastructures) to support them with their data production workflows.

This use case aims to advance the understanding and use of PIDs for instruments, such as instruments, devices, software and services, in the context of the PaN facilities. This is an area of great interest in the community, for example assisting with assessing the impact of individual instruments. The Research Data Alliance (RDA) has a [Working Group on Persistent Identification of Instruments](#) that takes a cross-domain approach, but its specific application to PaN has not been fully explored.

Within the PaN domain, there have been two recent important European projects, ExPaNDS (<https://www.expands.eu>) and PaNOSC (<https://www.panosc.eu>), which have come to an end after three years of work. STFC was part of ExPaNDS, which is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Photon and Neutron Data Service, and was a collaboration between ten national Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs) as well as EGI. ExPaNDS was founded on the ideals of FAIR data, and has produced many high-quality results for the PaN community. There were also some areas of great interest to the community that were not yet pursued, including PIDs for instruments (in this context an instrument is a beamline on a facility, and its associated equipment used for conducting analyses of particular types). This task within the FAIR-IMPACT project is an opportunity to take this further to advance FAIR in the photon and neutron community.

Challenges that need to be addressed

Within this use case, we will look at addressing the following challenges:

- Investigating through engagement with staff from [ISIS Neutron and Muon Source](#), the Central Laser Facility and Diamond Light Source, how PIDs for instruments may be useful for their data management tasks, how they would be used in practice by different stakeholders, what changes of practices might be needed, and what the implications are for the adoption of PIDs.
- Examining and elaborating use cases, especially assessing impact of instruments.
- Appropriately representing versioning as instruments are modified over time.

Expected impact of the Use Case

There is growing interest in assessing impact of research funding from different perspectives, including impact of whole facilities and of the instruments within them. The ability to refer to an instrument unambiguously through a PID would facilitate this assessment. Furthermore, it would enable credit to be clearly assigned to facilities staff responsible for particular instruments. We will explore these points with the facilities' staff.

Expected outputs

Through this use case, we expect to obtain a better understanding of facilities needs around identification of instruments, how this could be useful for their daily processes, how the generation and use of such PIDs could be handled, and how they could fit into the practices of photon and neutron facilities, as well as the use cases that motivate them.

By progressing the understanding and implications of PIDs for instruments for PaN facilities, we hope that a potential implementation of PIDs for instruments for these communities could be planned in future projects.

iv. UNIMAN

This use case is based around The University of Manchester's [WorkflowHub](#), a registry of computational workflows. Originating from the EOSC-Life Cluster, it is now used by over 190 research groups and projects from different disciplines, and has over 430 workflows registered. It is supported by multiple EOSC projects (EOSC-Life, BY-COVID, BioDT, EuroScienceGateway, BGE, Reliance, SKA, EOSC4Cancer etc.). It accommodates workflows of any type (e.g. Galaxy, CWL, Nextflow, Jupyter Notebook), supporting 18 different systems to date, with registration through repositories such as GitHub, or as a direct upload. WorkflowHub supports [RO-Crate](#) import and export adhering to the Workflow RO-Crate profile. There are various challenges resulting from various workflow components, such as software and data, inconsistent use of identifiers, the various inter-relations between components, and the details of the runs and types.

The overall goal of this use case is to encourage and support [FAIR Computational Workflows](#), where workflow systems help researchers in producing FAIR data and recording provenance of their analysis, but also where workflows themselves become FAIR scholarly objects in their own right, appear in the scholarly knowledge graph, cited in academic papers, etc.

To achieve this, we have proposed a multi-strand strategy (table below).

Task	Status
Improve and document explicit identification and linking (FAIR Signposting) from WorkflowHub to PIDs, metadata and RO-Crate downloads	WorkflowHub is an early implementer of FAIR Signposting ¹ using the patterns Bibliographic Metadata and Publication Boundary to signpost the RO-Crate. Updating to incorporate latest version of FAIR Signposting Currently, we are running a support offer focused on RO-Crate and FAIR Signposting, for which we have run 2 sessions online with applicants. WorkflowHub doing further work to reach FAIR Signposting Level 2 and align with FAIR Digital Object (FDO) patterns.
Software Hash Identifiers (SWHID) automatically requested and recorded when archiving a Git-based workflow in WorkflowHub	Planned investigation in European BioHackathon 2023 project #13: Discovering Bioinformatics Software in Software Heritage
Capture and expose PIDs for tools used by workflows (e.g. bio.tools, Bioconda) from Galaxy and other workflow systems	WorkflowHub entries can be annotated with tool PIDs, either by automatic parsing of the workflow description, or through a tagging mechanism that queries the bio.tools API. Further work will add these to the RO-Crate metadata.
Generating location-independent identifiers (RFC6920) for data generated by workflow	Ongoing as part of the Workflow Run RO-Crate profile task force.

¹ <https://signposting.org/adopters/#workflowhub>

runs, potentially large/sensitive, to be included in workflow provenance	
Leverage RO-Crate to capture and propagate workflow provenance outputs and related PIDs	A publication is close to submission on “Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate”.
Create RO-Crate profiles for capturing the provenance of an execution of a computational workflow with increasing granularity	Profiles for provenance capture have been released .
Define FAIR Computational Workflow principles	Initiated WCI working group FAIR Computational Workflows , gathering existing practices across workflow systems and drafting a paper.

b. PIDs in complex data citation

i. EMBL-EBI

European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) is Europe’s largest provider of public biomolecular data resources. The institute is co-located with Elixir Hub and partnered up in many relevant EU projects, among others EOSC-Life, FREYA, BY-COVID.

The ambition of EMBL-EBI in the PID use case is to curate and update components of Identifiers.org. The updates will be aligned with community standards and needs following FAIR practices. Up until now, a lot of the work was put into curating entries, resolving technical debt, providing user support, and solving any pending issues. We have also recently improvised tombstone information for deprecated entries and provide minimal support to sensitive information (see item b.ii below).

The ambition is to study the possibility of facilitating the automated use of the Identifiers.org registry. The Identifiers.org resolution service provides PIDs to data hosted by several repositories. The API endpoints of the service can already provide metadata information on the referenced objects. A team of specialists actively curates the entries of the registry to ensure correct behaviour and normalised information.

The service currently provides minimal support for PIDs intended for complex data, in cases where the target repository identifies these objects with local IDs and provides a valid URL pattern for redirection to these objects. Providing additional support in such cases is another action point for the use case to address. However, we still have to collect existing repositories of complex data, and identify the needs that Identifiers.org can address.

ii. INRAE

INRAE is the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment. It proposes, through research, innovation and support for public policies, new directions to support the emergence of sustainable agricultural and food systems.

INRAE is the first French institute to have a Department for Open Science.

The main goal of this use case is the production of a recommendations document on PIDs, to be adopted and applied in the Institute, and beyond. These recommendations concern different resources types, such as people, structures, events, sensors, documents and data. This document should help research teams choose the best type of identifier for the data they produce. It exposes all currently available services to produce a unique and permanent identifier based on the resource type (e.g., a service for assigning a DOI to a document; a service for creating and maintaining a SWHId representing open source software). We hope to publish the first version of the recommendations document by the end of 2023.

Additionally, as there is no service to permanently create and maintain URIs at the national level, we are currently building an information system capable of meeting these needs. This software will allow users to reserve a specific URI base (for example for a scientific program) and permanently store the corresponding URIs in a knowledge graph. The system will guarantee the uniqueness and accessibility of URIs, to meet the FAIR principles. We plan to open the first version of the system in the first quarter of 2024.

iii. LifeWatch ERIC

LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium dedicated to advancing e-Science research in biodiversity and ecosystem studies, supporting global sustainability challenges. Our mission involves uniting diverse scientific communities and creating a cutting-edge e-Science Research Infrastructure by connecting distributed observatories and research centres into unified accessible online platforms. A main component of our infrastructure, the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, underpinned by GeoNetwork, streamlines the management of metadata for various resource types, including Datasets, Research Sites, Services, Virtual Research Environments, and Workflows. It offers advanced search and user management functionalities, facilitating resource discovery and access

control. Furthermore, we leverage modern semantic technologies, offering a transformative approach to comprehensively describe and interconnect diverse data sources, reducing barriers to data exchange among researchers. To achieve this, LifeWatch ERIC's EcoPortal plays a crucial role in ecological research, providing a Semantic Artefact Repository that consolidates core ontologies, domain-specific vocabularies, and reference lists. It offers essential services to facilitate seamless discovery and integration, exemplifying our commitment to advancing scientific collaboration and knowledge management.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are fundamental in actualizing the FAIR principles within our infrastructure. EcoPortal facilitates the acquisition of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for hosted resources via Datacite services, concurrently offering the capability to specify authors and contributors through ORCID iD integration. Additionally, PIDs are instrumental in affiliating institutions through the Research Organization Registry (ROR). Within the LW ERIC Metadata Catalog, registered users seeking to create new resources (Datasets, Virtual Research Environments, etc.) must select the resource type and template, and provide mandatory metadata. This Catalogue facilitates the generation of DOIs for resources lacking them, leveraging the DataCite connection, following validation and verification. When it comes to workflow submissions, the challenge arises not only in assigning PIDs to the workflows themselves but also in allocating unique identifiers to each constituent service. This granular aspect of PIDs presents a pivotal consideration.

Managing dataset granularity in the Virtual Research Environment involves a critical question: how to handle the provenance of newly composed datasets? This challenge centres on deciding whether to assign DOI/PIDs to the entire dataset or its constituent provenance subsets. Another intricate issue is version granularity, which encompasses versioning of the entire artefact as well as individual entities, necessitating a clear linkage between deprecated and valid entities. Furthermore, we must establish a PID policy that aligns seamlessly with the EOSC Policy, ensuring compliance with essential standards. In response to these challenges, we're actively developing LifeBlock, a blockchain-based prototype. This innovative solution tracks all activities related to specific research objects, aiming to automate PID management through blockchain technologies. With LifeBlock, we're committed to enhancing our infrastructure's robustness, enabling more efficient management of complex datasets and their associated PIDs.

c. PIDs and sensitive data

i. EMBL-EBI

The ambition of EMBL-EBI in the PID use case is to curate and update components of Identifiers.org. The updates will be aligned with community standards and needs following FAIR practices. The ambition is to study the possibility of facilitating the automated use of

the Identifiers.org registry. The Identifiers.org resolution service provides PIDs to data hosted by several repositories. The API endpoints of the service can already provide metadata information on the referenced objects. A team of specialists actively curates the entries of the registry to ensure correct behaviour and normalised information.

Up until now, a lot of the work was put into curating entries, resolving technical debt, providing user support, and solving any pending issues. We have also recently improvised tombstone information for deprecated entries and provide minimal support to sensitive information.

By design, the service currently provides minimal support for PIDs intended for sensitive data. For these cases, the target repository identifies these objects with local IDs and provides a valid URL pattern for redirection to these objects. Additional support is provided by informing users of the authentication requirements to access this data and redirecting users according to their needs for more information. This was designed as such to maintain our core goal of maintaining our service as lightweight as possible and enforce that the data provider should manage, as much as possible, the processes related to their data, including authentication and authorization. We hope to evolve this feature as the needs of users and FAIR practices evolve.

ii. UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA ERIC

The UK Data Service (UKDS) is a partnership between the Universities of Essex, Manchester, UCL, Edinburgh and Jisc and the UK service provider to the Consortium of Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

The focus of this use case is on the research ‘studies’ of sensitive nature deposited at the UK Data Service and the subsequent derived data products. The sensitivity issue is the handling of information containing directly identifiable personal data or data that has the capacity to lead to reidentification, either through related variables within the dataset or through linkage with other data. We need to consider the implications involved in handling sensitive data for PID management and associated kernel metadata of a related identifier/object, e.g. for a repository identifier (“is currently approved to hold sensitive data”) or a researcher identifier (“has current credentials for accessing sensitive data”).

We will ensure the inclusiveness of metadata by considering the different requirements of PID management for digital objects beyond datasets. In CoreTrustSeal² terms, the focus is Digital Object Management. Version changes to a digital object can trigger many different

² <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

outcomes and the presence of sensitive data sets additional conditions on the digital object management process. Maintaining the provenance information is important throughout the process. Sensitive digital object may or may not be assigned a persistent identifier and associated sensitivity metadata during the Conceive, Create and Collect³ phase. At the point of deposit this sensitivity related information may already exist and need to be integrated, or the repository may be entirely responsible for the assignment and handling of the identifier and related metadata. Throughout the following work on curation, quality, compliance discovery, identification, access and reuse the sensitivity metadata may need to be updated as digital objects are copied, changed, versioned and linked.

Current work focuses on the baseline challenges of describing version management for sensitive data and is expanding into the more specific handling of metadata including that related to people, projects, reuse environments and data outputs.

8. Conclusions and next steps

Taking PIDs into use is not a very cumbersome nor difficult task per sé, however, applying good practices for PID implementation e.g. for a particular workflow or when working with a particular type of data, is not self-evident and is in need of further well-tested documentation. Through the work of the prominent eight use case partners involved in this task and research community involvement, this task is well-equipped to provide the research community with useful tips and guidance on how to implement PIDs in the most effective manner within research. Advancing machine-actionability, scientific reproducibility and research object type definitions when managing PIDs are also within the scope of this work and will provide a nuanced discussion on best practice implementation of PIDs. The lessons learned from this work will be translated across research domains to serve the broader research community and ultimately foster harmonised PID practices.

9. References

CNR: <https://www.cnr.it/en/about-us>

INRIA: <https://www.softwareheritage.org/#>

UKRI-STFC: <https://www.ukri.org/councils/stfc/>

UNIMAN: <https://www.manchester.ac.uk/>

EMBL-EBI: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about>

³ Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.76890>

INRAE: <https://www.inrae.fr/en/about-us>

LifeWatch ERIC: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/who-we-are/>

UESSEX-UKDS/CESSDA ERIC:

<https://www.cessda.eu/About/Consortium-and-Partners/List-of-Service-Providers/United-Kingdom-sp1927>

